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The Dual Impact of Organic Farming Support in Italy

Discussion paper

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Abstract

This paper investigates the abatement of farm-level greenhouse gas emissions as a response to the adoption of organic farming under the respective policy support. A theoretical framework of the farmers' decision-making accounts for response heterogeneity and makes the possible discrepancy between the private and societal objectives explicit. Causal machine learning estimation to admit treatment-effect heterogeneity across farm typologies is used. The study concerns the EU Common Agricultural Policy support to organic farming from 2015 to 2022 using a balanced panel of Italian Farm Accountancy Data Network units. The results confirm potential inconsistencies between private and societal objectives and bring into question the effectiveness of the policy support in terms of emission abatement.

1. Introduction

Agriculture significantly contributes to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, accounting for nearly 22% of total net anthropogenic emissions in 2019 (IPCC, 2022). To address this issue, the primary sector must implement strategies to reduce its carbon footprint (Clark et al., 2020). There exist several farming techniques that can help achieve emission reductions, with organic farming being a prominent example. Indeed, organic farming promotes the widespread adoption of agroecological practices, which may effectively curb farm-level carbon emissions (Smith et al., 2019a; Schievano et al., 2023; Le Gloux & Dupraz, 2024).

This idea is reflected in the European Union Action Plan for the development of organic production (European Commission, 2021). In its line of action '*Organics leading by example: improving the contribution of organic farming to sustainability*', the plan points out that organic farming uses several management practices that can mitigate the effects of climate change, with additional benefits for the environment and biodiversity. Therefore, supporting organic farming in the context of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) seems consistent with the emphasis given in the EU's strategies and planning. During the 2014-2020 CAP programming period, organic farming supported amounted to over €12 billion, mostly under CAP Pillar 2 (Stoltze et al., 2016; European Commission, 2021; European Court of Auditors, 2024). Since the conversion to organic is expected to be the primary contribution of the agricultural sector to climate change mitigation (European Commission: Directorate-General for Climate Action et al., 2024), the current CAP (2023–2027) will proceed in the same direction

Despite remaining a central instrument in the CAP agenda, the actual contribution of organic farming to reducing agricultural GHG emissions is still debated. Several studies have shown that, when the system-wide effects of organic farming are considered, the reduction in the carbon footprint through organic farming may be very low if not negligible (Smith et al., 2019a; Jansson et al., 2021). Even if the analysis concentrates on the in-farm carbon footprint at the individual level, the extent to which the support to organic farming changes behaviour is very different across farm typologies

(Martín-García et al., 2024; Coderoni, 2019). In this respect, the European Court of Auditors' (2024) special report on organic farming in the EU highlights that the CAP support helped to increase the EU's organic area, but its environmental impacts have not been sufficiently studied. The report attributes this lack of assessment to the fact that the EU strategy for organic farming lacks quantifiable objectives and clear indications on how to measure progress.

In this paper, we assess the reduction of farm-level GHG emissions as a response to the adoption of organic farming under the corresponding CAP support. Moreover, we also attempt to estimate how much society spends to obtain a unit of carbon dioxide (CO₂) abatement through organic farming subsidies. This research question raises two issues, one conceptual and the other methodological. The conceptual challenge is that in voluntarily adopting organic agriculture, farmers are driven by private objectives that do not correspond with society's environmental objectives, including the abatement of GHG emissions. The possible discrepancy between private and societal outcomes may lead to policy being ineffective and inefficient. Disarticulating these two possibly diverging outcomes requires the establishment of a theoretical foundation for farmers' decision making.

From a methodological perspective, we expect considerable heterogeneity in the response to organic support, as this heavily depends on farm-specific characteristics. While the same private outcome is pursued by all farmers, the desired societal outcome may only be observed for few farms under very specific conditions. This requires appropriate identification and estimation strategies that most conventional parametric or semi-parametric approaches to policy evaluation may not guarantee (Esposti, 2017a; 2017b; Bertoni et al., 2020; Bartolini et al., 2021). For this reason, we tackle the effect of organic farming on GHG emissions and farmers' private outcome using causal machine learning (CML) techniques (Storm et al., 2020; Stetter et al., 2022; Coderoni, Esposti & Varacca, 2024). The latter represents a reliable tool for understanding how and to what extent the effectiveness of CAP organic farm support varies across diverse farms.

Since the study concentrates on the 2014-2020 CAP programming period (which was extended to 2022), our empirical investigation exploits the 2015-2022 panel of Italian Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) farms. The results suggest possible inconsistency between the private and societal outcomes. Many farmers obtain a private advantage by adopting the measure, and, in some cases, this could make policy support redundant (or inefficient). At the same time, there is little, if any, accompanying societal outcome, which would imply the measure's limited effectiveness and high social cost.

2. Background and Overview of Literature

In 2022, 10.5% of the EU's total utilised agricultural area was farmed organically.¹ The gradual but continuous growth of organic farming in the EU has been supported by legal, strategic, and financial frameworks (European Court of Auditors, 2024; Abitabile, 2019). Financial support has mostly been provided through the CAP. The support is defined per unit of land (i.e., per ha), and a distinction is drawn between support for conversion and support for the maintenance of organic farming, with the former usually higher than the latter. In the 2014 to 2022 programming period, organic farming was supported under Measure 11, with a financial envelope representing about 10% of the total RDP allocation.

The current CAP (2023–2027) reinforced the climate objective of conventional agro-environmental measures, which have been redefined as agro-environmental and climate schemes. In some countries, there has been also an attempt to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of these measures by redesigning them according to a results-based rather than an action-based logic (Eichorn et al., 2024; Le Gloux & Dupraz, 2024).

Although CAP support helped increase the organic farming area, as stated by the European Court of Auditors (2024), the related environmental benefits were not always guaranteed. However,

¹ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/> (accessed 02/12/24).

according to what Member States have indicated in their CAP national strategic plans, the potential of organic farming to mitigate GHG emissions is expected to become particularly relevant. The European Commission has in fact recently published an analysis of the 2023 to 2027 CAP national strategic plans and their potential contribution to GHG reduction according to which the conversion to organic is expected to represent the primary contributor to climate change mitigation (European Commission: Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development – Unit A3, 2024). The latter, it is read, has the potential to avoid GHG emissions and increase carbon sequestration by an average of 6.57 million tonnes of CO_{2e} annually, thereby contributing to 21% of the total estimated mitigation potential of the CAP Strategic Plans at the EU level.

Existing studies on the potential of organic farming to mitigate GHG emissions have however produced mixed results. In an early detailed investigation of the environmental advantages of organic compared to conventional farming, Stolze et al. (2000) stressed the lack of reliable quantitative data and quantitative studies. They concluded that while GHG emissions seem lower in organic farming when considered on a per-hectare basis, on a per-unit of output scale the gap seems to disappear; any definite difference between the farming systems would point to the worse performance of organic farming.

This duality has seemingly persisted over the last two decades of study. The European Commission, in its ‘Guidance to Member States in improving the contribution of land-use, forestry and agriculture to enhance climate, energy and environment ambition’, assumes that the ban on the use of chemical nitrogen fertilisers in organic farming will not reduce GHG emissions. Moreover, emissions per unit of product may be considerably higher, primarily due to reduced output and the use of organic sources of nitrogen (Wiltshire et al., 2023). In this respect, Guerrero et al. (2024) quantify the environmental and climate impacts of sustainable farming practices based on data from meta-analyses; the effects of organic systems on GHG are reported for crops as changes in emissions per hectare. They reveal both positive (for N₂O and CH₄ for arable systems), negative (for CH₄ in rice paddies systems), as well as those that are non-significant changes (for N₂O for grasslands and

rice paddies). Similarly, Martín-García et al. (2024) point to modest changes in the (per hectare) environmental performance (including GHG emissions) of fruit producing farms that converted to organic farming, mainly because most farms formerly followed conventional practices characterised by less intensive input use.

The overall effect on GHG per unit of production is unclear and hard to predict. Indeed, several authors point to an important general issue, confirming what had already been stressed by Stolze et al. (2000). Some organic farming practices may reduce GHG emissions and increase carbon sequestration more than conventional farming (Muller and Aubert, 2014; Skinner et al., 2014; Smith et al., 2019b). However, these same practices may also reduce production (Scialabba et al., 2015; Smith et al., 2019a; Coderoni, 2019). This is also the conclusion of a meta-analysis of 71 studies at the European level, confirming that organic farming practices generally reduce the environmental impacts per unit of area but not necessarily per unit of product (Tuomisto et al., 2012).

Another major conclusion of these studies is that performances can be highly heterogeneous in terms of GHG emissions and production. As a result, any general conclusion on the contribution of organic farming to emission abatement is likely problematic. Approaches that admit treatment-effect heterogeneity and the different responses to support across diverse farm characteristics (e.g., farming conditions, types of farming, geographical location, and farm size) are thus especially relevant.

Despite this rich literature on the environmental impact of organic farming, particularly in the EU context, few studies explicitly attempt to associate this impact with a social cost and, consequently, to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of the policy measures. To the best of our knowledge, there is no study estimating the reduction of farm-level GHG emissions as a response to the adoption of organic farming under the CAP support measure and the associated social cost for

doing so.² Conversely, there is considerable empirical evidence on the cost of mitigating GHG emissions in farming. This literature adopts the concept of marginal abatement cost to express the explicit and implicit costs private agents incur whenever they choose, or are forced, to reduce emissions. The values these studies reflect for the last decade are generally lower than the EU ETS prices (i.e., from €10 to €50/tonne CO₂). These charges could be intended as a benchmark in the event of the introduction of an agricultural carbon tax (Coderoni, Dell’Unto & Cortignani, 2024; Stepanyan et al., 2023).³ However, the charges are also largely heterogeneous across farming conditions and, above all, rapidly growing with the increase in abatement efforts (Huber et al., 2023).

Recently, some governments (Denmark and New Zealand, for instance) have proposed or announced the introduction of a carbon tax (or an ETS) specifically for agriculture (animal productions, in particular), and such cases may be informative regarding the policy or collective monetary evaluation of the social cost of emission abatement. For instance, the Danish government recently proposed the introduction of a tax starting at €16/tonne CO₂ eq., increasing to €40/tonne CO₂ eq. from 2035 onwards (Blanford, 2024).

However, to date, there has been no estimation of the cost associated with reducing GHG emissions due to CAP support. For this reason, our study specifically addressed this knowledge gap.

3. Theoretical Framework: Farmer Decision Making and Policy Effectiveness

We establish our framework by first considering a panel of N production units (farms) observed over S time periods. For any i -th farm ($i = 1, \dots, N$) in time t ($t = 1, \dots, S$), an aggregated multi-input multi-output production technology can be represented by the feasible production set $F_{it} \subset \mathbb{R}^M$. Notice that F_{it} is farm-specific and accounts for all sources of heterogeneity in the farmer’s

² A Scopus search with the keywords: ‘organic farm*’ AND ‘cap’ OR ‘common agricultural policy’ OR ‘policy support’ AND ‘GHG’, returned no pertinent results.

³ In performing their simulations of the possible impact of an agricultural carbon tax under alternative scenarios, Stepanyan et al. (2023) consider a tax of 100€/tonne CO₂ and Coderoni, Dell’Unto and Cortignani (2024) a tax of 25, 50 or 100€/tonne CO₂.

decision to voluntarily adopt policy measures and production choices (Esposti, 2024). In particular, F_{it} depends on external and internal factors that we generally indicate with the $(Q \times 1)$ vector, \mathbf{X}_{it} . Depending on the field, these are sometimes referred to as covariates, control variables or confounders and can include either observable farm features, unobservable characteristics, or both. Next, we define a $(M \times 1)$ vector of netputs $\mathbf{Y}_{it} = (Y_{it1}, \dots, Y_{itM})'$ containing farm outputs (with a positive sign) and inputs (with a negative sign). These netputs are only feasible if $\mathbf{Y}_{it} \in F_{it}$.

Suppose now that, at any given time t , each farm is offered the opportunity to voluntarily participate in a policy (or, alternatively, a treatment), T_{it} . If that farm chooses to participate (i.e., $T_{it} = 1$), then this choice is expected to induce specific production choices, \mathbf{Y}_{it} . Therefore, for any given farm, we assume that the treatment can be univocally mapped onto production choices ($T_{it} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{Y}_{it}$). It is thus possible to express these choices, as well as the resulting economic and environmental performance of farms, as a function of both the treatment and the aforementioned farm characteristics, \mathbf{X}_{it} . In other words, we can write $\mathbf{Y}_{it} = f(T_{it}, \mathbf{X}_{it})$, where $f(\cdot)$ is a vector-valued function.

As noted in Section 1, the voluntary policy measure considered here promotes organic farming with the goal of reducing the environmental impact of conventional agricultural practices (i.e., Measure 11 of the CAP; see Section 4.1 for details). Therefore, if farm i adopts organic farming and receives the corresponding support, $T_{it} = 1$.⁴ Within this theoretical framework, if both \mathbf{Y}_{it} and T_{it} are observable $\forall i \in 1, \dots, N$ and $\forall t \in 1, \dots, S$, at least two different treatment effects of participating in the organic-farming intervention can be defined. The first treatment effect concerns the outcome of interest to the farmers, namely their profit (or net farm income - NI; see Section 4). Therefore, if the i -th farm chooses to opt into the treatment at time t ($T_{it} = 1$), what matters to the farmer is the

⁴ It is worth stressing that, in the FADN dataset, both the dummy 'organic' and the extent of policy support are provided. The underlying assumption here is that these two conditions always correspond: whenever a farm is organic it receives the support and vice versa. The very few cases in which this condition is not met for whatever reason (organic but not supported farms and supported but not organic farms) are thus excluded from the analysis (see Section 4).

potential effect of this choice on their profit, p_{it} . The generic farm-specific profit function can thus be expressed as follows:

$$p_{it} = p[f(T_{it}, \mathbf{X}_{it})], \quad (1)$$

where $p(\cdot)$ is a single-valued function. The first treatment effect associated with the organic support policy can thus be expressed as follows:

$$D\pi_{it} = [(\pi_{it}|T_{it} = 1, \mathbf{X}_{it}) - (\pi_{it}|T_{it} = 0, \mathbf{X}_{it})] = p[Df(T_{it}, \mathbf{X}_{it})]$$

$$\text{where } Df(\cdot) = DY_{it} = [(Y_{it}|T_{it} = 1, \mathbf{X}_{it}) - (Y_{it}|T_{it} = 0, \mathbf{X}_{it})]. \quad (2)$$

The second treatment effect of interest concerns the outcome relevant to society (or the policy maker), namely improved environmental performance. Assuming that the production choice implied by \mathbf{Y}_{it} univocally determines the environmental performance of farm i , let \mathbf{E}_{it} be a $P \times 1$ vector of environmental indicators. Production choices can thus be mapped into environmental indicators ($\mathbf{Y}_{it} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{E}_{it}$). If the interest is in a particular measure of environmental performance (such as farm-level GHG emissions, as in the present case), E_{it} can be reduced to a scalar term.⁵ As a result, farm-level environmental performance can be expressed as $E_{it} = g(T_{it}, \mathbf{X}_{it})$, where $g(\cdot)$ is a single-valued function. Consequently, the second treatment effect can be expressed as follows:

$$DE_{it} = [(E_{it}|T_{it} = 1, \mathbf{X}_{it}) - (E_{it}|T_{it} = 0, \mathbf{X}_{it})] = Dg(T_{it}, \mathbf{X}_{it}) \quad (3)$$

Notice that the definition of profit employed throughout does not include the policy subsidy (this can also be referred to as before-support farm profit).⁶ Therefore, we argue that the farmers' voluntary choice to participate in the treatment implies that $(\Delta\pi_{it} + S_{it}) \geq 0$, where S_{it} represents the monetary support received by farm i at time t to adopt organic farming. At the same time, policy makers expect $DE_{it} \leq 0$. Therefore, conditions $(D\pi_{it} + S_{it}) \geq 0$ and $DE_{it} \leq 0$ can be regarded as

⁵ Though organic farming may bring about several societal objectives, of which GHG emission reduction is just one, it is here considered as exemplary given its societal relevance.

⁶ As clarified in Section 4, this is the definition of the outcome variable adopted in the present empirical analysis; it is also the variable provided within the FADN dataset.

regularities, namely, they are expected to be observed, on average, within a farm population or sample. However, since both $D\pi_{it}$ and DE_{it} are expected to also be highly heterogeneous across values of X_{it} (i.e., farm-specific), it is possible that opposite signs might be observed, in practice, at the farm level.⁷

The possible farm-level discrepancy between $D\pi_{it}$ and DE_{it} has major implications for policy evaluation. In general, the policy under consideration can be understood as both effective and efficient if the amount of subsidy to switch from conventional to organic farming is (i) strictly necessary to adopt the new technology and (ii) yields the intended environmental goal. Policy effectiveness thus concerns the extent of the social outcome that can be generated by the policy. In the present case, we can only properly evaluate policy effectiveness for those units in which $DE_{it} \leq 0$. Policy efficiency, by contrast, improves whenever the same societal outcome can be obtained through lower public expenditure. Therefore, evaluating efficiency requires not only DE_{it} , but also the private outcome, $D\pi_{it}$. Such involvement takes three forms.

First, a negative $D\pi_{it}$ implies additional costs for society. As such, whenever $D\pi_{it} < 0$, the actual cost of the policy should be expressed as $S_{it} - D\pi_{it}$. Second, all expenditure, S_{it} , exceeding the loss of profit, that is, $(S_{it} + D\pi_{it} | D\pi_{it} < 0) > 0$, can be interpreted as a redundant, namely inefficient, expenditure. Ideally, efficient expenditure should meet the condition $(S_{it} + D\pi_{it} | D\pi_{it} < 0) = 0$, which would correspond to the minimum expenditure required to make the adoption of organic farming economically convenient. Finally, positive $D\pi_{it}$ might be considered as beneficial as this would reduce the net social cost of the policy. At the same time, positive changes in profit would also imply that the public contribution, S_{it} , is redundant; in other words, the corresponding societal outcome, DE_{it} , would have been obtained regardless of the policy support granted to organic farmers.

⁷ As argued by Esposti (2024), non-monetary motivations for farmers' adoption of organic farming might justify a negative profit outcome for the treatment, that is, $(D\pi_{it} + S_{it}) < 0$ (see also Kremmydas et al., 2023), while specific internal and external farming conditions might also imply the adoption of organic farming has a negative environmental impact ($DE_{it} < 0$).

4. Data and Research Design

4.1. The Sample and Treatment Sets

Our empirical study focuses on Italy, one of the EU countries with the largest share of utilised agricultural area (UAA) cultivated with organic farming techniques. In 2022, Italy ranked third in the EU after France and Spain, and in 2023, there was significant growth in the share of agricultural land used for organic farming, reaching 19.8% of the total Italian UAA. In addition, the diversity of farming conditions and types in Italian agriculture (Baltoni et al., 2021) inevitably impacts the environmental impact of the farming activities (Coderoni and Esposti, 2018). The country is thus particularly interesting for assessing the heterogeneous impact of organic farming across different farm specialisations and structures.

We use information from the 2015-2022 Italian FADN dataset.⁸ Our initial sample consists of a representative collection of Italian commercial farms in the form of an unbalanced panel consisting of 9,569 observations in 2015, 10,153 in 2016, 10,792 in 2017, 10,769 in 2018, 10,805 in 2019, 10,764 in 2020, 11,040 in 2021 and 11,084 in 2022. Although the programming period covered the period from 2014 to 2022, in Italy, the new RDP only entered into force in 2015. Therefore, the period of policy implementation under analysis (and the consequent sample) is 2015 to 2022.⁹ Our sample definition begins by extracting a balanced panel (3,899 units). Next, units with a change in the treatment status during the period (927) are removed. As a result, a balanced panel of 2,972 always-treated and never-treated units observed over eight years is obtained. Among these individuals, 297 (10% of the sample) are organic farms¹⁰, while the remaining 2,675 provide a

⁸ At the time of writing, validated FADN data for 2023 had yet to be released and, in any case, this year would refer, at least partially, to the new CAP regime (2023-2027) that started on 1st January 2023.

⁹ As documented in Section 4.3, we also use the 2008–2014 Italian FADN dataset to define pre-treatment covariates.

¹⁰ Note that this split approximately maintains the organic to conventional proportion observed in the Italian farm population (<https://www.isprambiente.gov.it/it/attivita/biodiversita/ispra-e-la-biodiversita/articoli/crece-il-biologico-migliora-l-ambiente>).

comprehensive control group that can be used to define appropriate counterfactual evidence to identify the effect under investigation. Table 1 summarises this sample composition.

We further collapse the 2015–2022 panel into a cross-sectional sample of 2,972 units,¹¹ where, for every individual, variables are defined as multi-annual averages (or model values) calculated over the years of observation.¹² On the one hand, this makes sure that the typical year-by-year volatility of farm economic performances, including in the indicators employed to derive the outcome variables (see Section 4.2), is marginalized over in the data. Secondly, we restrict the comparison not between conventional farms and organic farms with different years of experience with the new farming techniques (i.e., staggered adoption – Callaway and Sant’Anna, 2021), but we only look at units that either passed the conversion period and decided to stay organic and the always conventional ones. In other words, our identification and estimation strategy do not make use of the time dimension.

Finally, we define the “treatment” variable as binary indicator which equals one in case of receiving the CAP support for organic farming. Specifically, the support for organic farming falls within the RDP Measures 11.1 and 11.2 in the programming period under consideration (see Stolze et al., 2016).¹³

[Table 1 here]

11 For a similar empirical strategy see also Quemada et al. (2020). Since here we are not pooling data within the panel but are simply using the averages over the periods, the size of the samples is not NT but simply N.

12 We only consider the policy when it is fully operational, and we disregard the adjustment farms undertake just after entering the policy itself. For this reason, although the period under consideration is 2015–2022, the outcome variables (see Section 4.2) are computed as an average over only the last three years (2020–2022) to obtain more robust evidence while still concentrating only on the consolidated (that is, stabilised) response to the policy.

13 Organic farms might not all have received the specific support, both because regional resources are not sufficient to meet all requests for access to individual measures and because not all organic farms choose to apply for support, especially in relation to the maintenance of the organic production method. In the present case, however, these cases are very few and, as already mentioned, have been excluded from the sample.

4.2. Outcome Variable Definition

As elaborated in Section 3, two distinct outcome variables are considered, one indicating the private objective ($D\pi$ of the theoretical model), the other indicating the societal objective (DE). The former is empirically expressed by the variation of the net farm income (NI) as reported by the FADN dataset and does not include the policy support to organic farming (as for any other RDP measure). The latter uses the FADN data to calculate the emission-intensity indicators through farms' economic and structural characteristics (Coderoni, 2019; Coderoni and Vanino, 2022). This approach is an adaptation of the methodology employed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2006) that computes emissions at the farm level, up to the farm gate, using emission factors derived from national inventories (ISPRA, 2021) and activity data derived from the FADN.¹⁴ The approach is an established international standard already widely used in the literature as a farm-level indicator of GHG emissions (Dabkiene, 2017; Dabkiene et al., 2020; Coderoni and Esposti, 2018; Baldoni et al., 2017, 2018, 2023).

A practical problem for both outcome variables (NI and GHG) is that they are highly size dependent. This dependency can only be partially controlled by including economic size in the covariate set, as it cannot be excluded that there is a remaining size bias. Therefore, both outcome variables are made size-independent by dividing by the farms' annual standard output (SO). The two outcome variables considered here are the following: the variation of the farm, NI, divided by SO (NI/SO), the variation of the farm's GHG emission expressed in kg CO_{2eq.}, divided by SO (GHG/SO). This same solution (of dividing by farm SO) is adopted for all size-dependent covariates (see next Section).

¹⁴ For further details on the methodology please refer to Coderoni and Vanino (2022).

4.3. Covariate set

Following Coderoni, Esposti and Varacca (2024) and Esposti (2024), we argue that unknown firm-specific technology is one of the major confounders in the analysis of the effect of switching to organic farming. Confounding variables are therefore selected to represent the key features of this underlying technology such that any interaction among these covariates can also serve as a sensible proxy for unobserved features that potentially correlate with farm technology. This approach is particularly relevant when estimating causal effects, which involves outcome modelling via ML methods.

Borrowing from Brown et al. (2021) and Stetter et al. (2022), we inform farm technology through $P = 48$ observed covariates that we cluster in the following farm-attribute sets: cost structure, size, and economic endowment; environmental and geographical factors; socio-demographic characteristics; production specialization; crop mix; and input intensity. Table A1 in Annex 1 maps each confounder with the covariate group to which it belongs. At first, the number of controls included in Table A1 might seem large relative to the sample size. However, unlike most parametric techniques, the algorithms discussed in Section 5 can easily accommodate arbitrarily large collections of information and use regularisation techniques to automatically drop either redundant features or irrelevant covariates that contribute little to variability in the outcome variable. Yet, since the latter is a purely data-driven operation, there is a non-zero chance that out-of-the-box application of such methods will result in discarding information that is unimportant in predicting the outcome but potentially highly correlated with the treatment assignment. When this happens, the resulting causal estimates might be unreliable due to a form of bias that is generally known as either regularisation bias or regularisation-induced confounding (RIC). We return to this concept in Section 5, where we explain how the proposed methods should safeguard against this problem.

All these covariates constitute the $Q \times 1$ vector, \mathbf{X}_i , discussed in Section 3 and enter the estimation stage as pre-2015 averages. In the case of categorical variables for which a change is

observed, we use the prevalent category over the period. Since confounders must be pre-determined with respect to the treatment (a condition known as exogeneity), we only consider values of \mathbf{X} preceding the observation of the policy treatment (starting in 2015). This strategy is commonly adopted in the empirical literature (see, for example, Bertoni et al., 2020; Uehleke et al., 2022; Stetter et al., 2022; Coderoni, Esposti and Varacca, 2024) and should safeguard against unintended causal paths from the treatment to the covariates. For this reason, we remove all farms for which pre-treatment covariates (i.e., pre-2015 observations for \mathbf{X}_i) are not available. Pre-2015 averages are computed for every farm, using all available observations over the period from 2008 to 2014. Clearly, this requires assuming there is no anticipation effect on either of the outcome variables of adopting organic farming.

Finally, since the original FADN sample contains several implausible covariate values, before estimating Models (4) and (5), we look for observations for which (i) any observed confounders exceeded the 99th percentile of the corresponding marginal covariate distribution across individuals and (ii) the calculated shares for cultivated crops, UAA and gross production do not sum to one. With respect to these extreme instances, we adopt a two-stage approach to avoid discarding a large amount of information. First, we drop all individuals for which condition (ii) is met. Second, rather than eliminating farms matching condition (i), we impute these implausible covariate observations using a simple regression-based strategy.¹⁵ Compared to the original sample illustrated above, the resulting sample (which we refer to as the ‘estimation sample’) comprises 2,187 farms, split between 212 treated and 1,976 untreated units (Table 1, lower part).

5. Methodology

We estimate the heterogeneous treatment effects of adopting organic farming using CML (see Brand et al., 2023 for a comprehensive overview). Specifically, we employ Bayesian Causal Forests

¹⁵ We begin by creating a subsample where all extreme values are removed; the latter are then employed to train an off-the-shelf random forest which we use to predict all the outliers (i.e., out of sample prediction).

(BCFs; Hahn et al., 2020). Unlike naïve applications of the standard Bayesian Additive Regression Tree (BART) algorithms, BCFs are designed to tackle the RIC issue mentioned in Section 4.3. Like other tree-based methods, BART algorithms can fit complex functional forms by creating regularised ensembles of shallow Bayesian trees (Chipman et al., 1998) while opening the possibility for predictive inference using the posterior distributions of the leaf parameters (Chipman et al., 2010). These methods show encouraging performance in terms of unbiasedness and coverage (Dorie et al., 2019; Carvalho et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2020) and allow access to a fully probabilistic (i.e., Bayesian) inferential approach. This allows us to quantify uncertainty when comparing different subgroups of individuals and facilitates the study of overlap between treated and untreated units (Hill & Su, 2013; Li et al., 2022).

To reduce the risk of RIC when fitting BART algorithms to estimate heterogeneous treatment effects, Hahn et al. (2020) propose a re-parameterisation of the outcome equation, with separate models fitted to the treatment-effect parameter and a prognostic component. Specifically, the variables included in the latter correspond to the full set of confounders discussed in Section 4.3, plus the estimated propensity score (PS) for participating in organic farming. The former component, on the other hand, includes only a subset of moderating variables¹⁶ that explain treatment heterogeneity. Under this configuration, the outcome model can be written as:

$$\mathbb{E}[Y_i | T_i = t_i, \mathbf{X}_i = \mathbf{x}_i] = f(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i) = m(\mathbf{x}_i, \hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}_i)) + \tau(\mathbf{w}_i)t_i \quad (4)$$

Where, $Y_i \in \{\pi_i, E_i\}$, $m(\cdot)$ indicates the prognostic function (i.e., the conditional mean of Y when the treatment is set to zero), $\hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}_i)$ is the estimated PS, while $\tau(\cdot)$ corresponds to the heterogeneous treatment effect with $\mathbf{w}_i \subset \mathbf{x}_i$. The latter is also known as the conditional average treatment effect

16 In our application, this subset includes moderators for (i) farm size (UAA); (ii) farm specialization (livestock, annual crops, perennial crops, mixed); (iii) farm gross production (total, crops, livestock, transformed and quality products); (iv) livestock endowment and crop mix; (v) input use (pesticides, N, P, K fertilisers); (vi) environmental and geographical factors.

(CATE) or, as introduced in Lechner (2018) and Knaus (2022), the individualised average treatment effect (IATE).

Technically, BART are prior distributions over functions that, coupled with a suitable likelihood for the outcome term, Y , yield the full Bayesian model (Betancourt, 2021) and, consequently, a posterior distribution for $\tau(\cdot)$ from which we can sample using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods (Gelman et al., 2013; McElreath, 2020). We indicate this probabilistic structure as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
m(\mathbf{x}_i) &\sim \text{BART}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}_i), \mathbf{x}_i) \\
\tau(\mathbf{w}_i) &\sim \text{BART}(\boldsymbol{\vartheta}|\mathbf{w}_i) \\
Y &\sim N(f(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i), \sigma^2) \\
\sigma^2 &\sim \text{Inv}\chi^2(\omega),
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where the hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, $\boldsymbol{\vartheta}$, and ω are selected based on the predictive performance of m on a validation set obtained through data splitting. The main object that we work with in the remainder of the analysis is the posterior distribution of $\tau(\mathbf{w}_i)$, which we refer to as $\phi(\tau(\mathbf{w}_i)|\mathbf{w}_i, t_i, y_1, \dots, y_N)$, where $\phi(\cdot)$ represents a generic probability density function. This is empirically represented as $\{\tau^s(\mathbf{w}_i)\}_{s=1}^S$, where S indicates the number of MCMC simulations.

Another advantage of adopting the parametrisation of Equation (4) is that it allows for regularising $\tau(\cdot)$ directly and independently of $m(\cdot)$, reducing the noisiness of the corresponding estimates. This approach offers a practical advantage over the so-called T-learners, where $\tau(\cdot)$ is estimated by simply fitting $m_1(\mathbf{x}_i) = \mathbb{E}[Y_i|T_i = 1, \mathbf{X}_i = \mathbf{x}_i]$ and $m_0(\mathbf{x}_i) = \mathbb{E}[Y_i|T_i = 0, \mathbf{X}_i = \mathbf{x}_i]$, and taking their difference typically produces larger standard errors. Furthermore, the additive nature

of Equation (4) ensures that the prior on $f(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i)$ remains a BART (Chipman et al., 2010; Hill et al., 2020).¹⁷

Finally, it is worth remembering that $\tau(\cdot)$ can be deemed causal only if three restrictions on the data-generating process are met. These assumptions are common in the causal inference literature and have already been postulated when applying these methods to study the RDP measures using FADN data (Arata & Sckokai, 2016; Stetter et al., 2022; Coderoni, Esposti & Varacca, 2024). In particular, we assume that: (i) conditional on the full set of pre-treatment covariates, \mathbf{X}_i , the distribution of the potential outcomes is independent of the treatment; that is, $Y_i(0), Y_i(1) \perp T_i | \mathbf{X}_i$ (unconfoundedness); (ii) there are no spillover effects and no alternative version of the treatment (stable unit treatment value assumption - SUTVA); (iii) we can always find comparable individuals in either of the two treatment cohorts for different configurations of \mathbf{X}_{it} , i.e., $0 < Pr(T_i = 1 | \mathbf{X}_{it} = \mathbf{x}_{it}) < 1$ (overlap).

Since assumptions (i) to (iii) are key to the identification of the IATEs, we run a series of robustness checks to probe the sensitivity of our results to these restrictions. Specifically, Annex 3 shows that condition (iii) is reasonable given our farm sample, although unconfoundedness and SUTVA are harder to investigate using observed data. Indeed, testing the spillover effect of adopting organic farming requires observing neighbouring farms and explicitly accounting for the corresponding spatial structure. Unfortunately, not only is this information missing in the FADN, but incorporating a network structure in Equation (4) has so far received little attention in the literature (Baldoni & Esposti, 2024). On the other hand, unconfoundedness can be partially investigated through a series of sensitivity tests addressing the stability of our results to violations of this assumption. These are also discussed in Appendix 3. Overall, these robustness checks suggest that caution is needed with respect to the unconfoundedness assumption, as the results might be

¹⁷ The model presented in Equation (4) is also used by Nie and Wager (2021), who discuss a frequentist approach to estimating $\tau(\mathbf{w}_i)$ which relies on a slightly different residuals-on-residuals re-parametrisation.

susceptible to the omission of important common causes of the treatment and the outcome that have little or no association with the full set of control variables. Given the comprehensiveness of the latter (see Annex 1, Table A1), these instances are unlikely in the present case but still worth considering.

6. Results and Discussion

6.1. Individualised Average Treatment Effects

Figure 1 displays the estimated maximum-a-posterior (MAP; the average over the S samples from the posterior distribution of $\tau(\mathbf{w}_i)$) and corresponding 95% credible intervals (CrI) of the IATEs for the two outcome variables, NI ($D\pi_i$) and GHG (DE_i) variation, respectively. Figures also exhibit the IATEs' average, typically known as average treatment effect (ATE), calculated as follows:

$$\tau^s = \int d\mathbf{w}_i \tau(\mathbf{w}_i)^s \phi_{\mathbf{w}_i}(\mathbf{w}_i) \quad (6)$$

Table 2 complements Figure 1 by summarising the findings in tabular form.

We begin by discussing the private outcome, i.e., the variation in NI. The ATE suggests a modest increase in NI of about €0.09 per € of SO, and approximately 80% of farms in the IATE distribution also show income growth. However, significant heterogeneity exists, as only 6% of farms have a clearly positive treatment effect where the credible interval CrI does not include zero (Figure 1a, left and central panels, and Table 2, upper part). This variability indicates that the financial benefits of switching to organic practices are not uniform across all farms. Consequently, while organic farming may slightly enhance farm-level NI, this effect cannot be generalized to all adopters. Therefore, we need to further explore treatment-effect heterogeneity to better understand which features drive these diverse farm responses. We discuss this approach in Section 6.2.

Regarding the societal outcome of GHG emission reduction, the ATE points to a minor decrease of approximately 0.05 kg CO₂eq per € of SO, with 75% of farms showing emission reductions in the IATE distribution. Nonetheless, the interval estimates reveal no effect at the individual farm level, as all CrIs include zero and the overall posterior distribution centers around

zero (Figure 1b, left and central panel, and Table 2, lower part). This suggests that, on average, adopting organic farming does not seem to have a clear impact on GHG emissions.

[Figure 1 and Table 2 here]

Following Section 3, another key difference between the two outcome variables relates to the policy implications of the IATE and ATE estimates. For the private outcome, these impacts assess the effectiveness and efficiency of the measures supporting organic farming. Since NI does not include policy support, the actual impact on farm-level income is the sum of the estimated IATE for NI and the observed policy support. The lack of a non-zero effect on NI for most farms therefore suggests that the policy support effectively makes adopting organic farming economically viable.

However, there is potential to improve policy efficiency. For the 6% of farms where organic farming clearly increases NI, monetary support may be unnecessary and could be saved without affecting adoption rates. Additionally, no farms show a clear negative impact on NI, indicating rational decision-making by farmers and the potential to reduce monetary support while maintaining adoption, as non-monetary motivations appear marginally relevant (Esposti, 2024).

For the societal outcome, the policy implications differ. The ATE indicates a slight reduction in emissions (approximately 0.05 kg CO₂eq per € of SO), with 75% of farms showing reductions in the IATE distribution. However, interval estimates reveal no conclusive effect at the individual farm level, as CrIs include zero and the overall posterior distribution centers around zero. This raises questions about the effectiveness of organic farming support in achieving emission abatement, despite its consistent support for farm-level income. Nonetheless, effectiveness might be improved within more homogeneous farm sub-groups, as explored in Section 6.2.

Using these estimates and Section 3's framework, we can perform a back-of-the-envelope calculation of policy effectiveness and efficiency. While the treatment effect for GHG abatement (DE_i) should be interpreted cautiously, it still offers insights into policy performance. Effectiveness is assessed by summing individual DE_i s for farms showing emission abatement ($DE_i < 0$ or *abating*

farms).¹⁸ To account for private outcomes ($D\pi_i$), farms with a positive IATE for NI ($0 \notin \text{CrI}$) have their DE_i excluded from the computation. The social cost is then calculated by subtracting $D\pi_i$ from policy expenditure ($S_i - D\pi_i$) for all farms, which is then divided by the total societal outcome, yielding a rough social cost per unit of emission abatement.

This calculation can be performed either for all farms (treated and untreated units) or exclusively for organic farms (treated units). For organic farms, the computation can be performed by considering the observed S_i . By contrast, non-organic farms are assigned an estimated counterfactual expenditure \tilde{S}_i using the prognostic component of model (4). We estimate a unit social cost of €2,972/tonne CO_{2eq} for all units, while the corresponding value for the organic cohort is approximately €1,928/tonne CO_{2eq}. When considering expenditure efficiency by minimizing the necessary support¹⁹, these costs drop to €233/tonne CO_{2eq} and €159/tonne CO_{2eq}, respectively. Although informative, these figures are relatively high compared to other carbon pricing levels, indicating significant potential for improving policy expenditure efficiency.²⁰

6.2. Group Average Treatment Effects

The set of posterior draws $\{\tau^S(\mathbf{w}_i)\}_{S=1}^S$, approximates a multivariate probability distribution over a P-dimensional function and, as such, might be difficult to interpret without reducing the problem to a smaller space. In this section, we investigate IATE heterogeneity by comparing farm

¹⁸ The implicit underlying assumption is that the observed positive variations ($DE_i > 0$) are negligible and, in any case, they are not the consequence of the adoption of organic farming but of some other (mostly unobserved) farmers' choices or characteristics.

¹⁹ As discussed in Section 3, this minimum expenditure is equal to $-D\pi_i$ for those units for which the estimated IATE implies $D\pi_i < 0$, and in this case the actual social cost simply is $-2D\pi_i$, while it is 0 for those units for which the estimated IATE implies $D\pi_i > 0$.

²⁰ For reference, it is worth noting that, in the last several years, the price of a unit of CO₂ emission in the EU ETS has ranged from €50/tonne CO₂ to €100/tonne CO₂ (Sitarz et al., 2024). In the farming sector, during the last decade, a large literature has provided values that are lower but not much different from ETS prices (from €10 to €100/tonne CO₂) (Coderoni, Dell'Unto, and Cortignani, 2024). Finally, the recent proposal of the Danish government to introduce a carbon price specifically for agriculture (animal production in particular) would consist of a tax starting at €16/tonne CO₂ eq. and then growing to €40/tonne CO₂ eq. from 2035 onwards (Blanford, 2024).

subgroups obtained through projections of this full posterior distribution onto the covariate space. Specifically, we follow the approach discussed in Hahn et al. (2020), Yeager et al. (2019) and Coderoni, Esposti, and Varacca (2024), who suggest eliciting the relevant subgroups by partitioning the IATE's MAP estimates, $\check{\tau}_i = S^{-1} \sum_{s=1}^S \tau_q^s(\mathbf{w}_i)$, using regression trees (CART; Breiman et al., 1984), where $\check{\tau}_i$ is split along \mathbf{w}_i . This approach to the subgroup search allows for flexible, functional forms and high levels of interpretability, uncovering the moderators that best predict the heterogeneous effects.²¹ Once the partitioning rules have been obtained, GATEs can be simply calculated as weighted averages of the IATEs within each tree leaf:²²

$$\check{\tau}^s(\mathbf{g}_i) = \int d\mathbf{w}_i \check{\tau}(\mathbf{w}_i)^s \phi_{\mathbf{w}_i | \mathbf{G}_i = \mathbf{g}_i}(\mathbf{w}_i), \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{G}_i denotes the collection of all the potential groups, and \mathbf{g}_i denotes one such group.

Figure 2 shows the (regularised) trees estimated by regressing $\check{\tau}_i^{NI}$ (Figure 2.a) and $\check{\tau}_i^{GHG}$ (Figure 2.b) on \mathbf{w}_i , respectively, while the upper part (Part A) of Tables 3 and Table 4 report these results in tabular form. The shallow tree for $\check{\tau}_i^{NI}$ (Figure 1a) and Table 3, Part A) highlights three modelling variables with high predictive power for the heterogeneous effects of organic practices on farm-level NI: the share of land cultivated with grapes, the share of gross production from livestock, and the intensity of use of phosphate fertilisers. Four of the CrI (both 95% and 90%) for the GATEs include only positive variation, indicating the presence of significant heterogeneity in the treatment effect. The subgroup for which the strongest (i.e., more positive) effect is observed consists of farms specialising in grape production that use more than 6.2 tonnes of phosphate fertilisers per hectare per year. Likewise, the second highest effect is found among similar farms that, conversely, use less fertilisers. These farmers are those who could potentially benefit more, in NI terms, by adopting organic farming.

²¹ We do not allow the trees to split more than three times to facilitate interpretability.

²² Calculating GATEs using the approach described above is also consistent with Lechner (2018), who constructs group-level effects as convex combinations of the IATEs. In our application, weighting is automatically performed when fitting the tree.

The fitted tree for $\check{\tau}_i^{GHG}$ highlights four variables with high predictive power for the heterogeneous effect of organic farming on GHG emissions: farm type, altitude, the intensity of use of phosphate fertilisers, and cereals as a share of farm UAA. Ignoring for a moment the high variance of the implied GATE, it is interesting to note that the group with the highest point estimate of GHG emissions reduction is composed of farms cultivating more than 16% of their UAA with cereals, distributing less than 1.7 tonnes of phosphate fertilisers per hectare and focusing on either annual crops or annual crops and livestock breeding (see Table 4, part A). Therefore, the difference in GHG emissions for the farms potentially most impacted and their emissions had they adopted organic farming results in the most negative GATE. Unlike the findings obtained for NI, however, our findings suggest limited treatment effect heterogeneity for $\check{\tau}_i^{GHG}$ (i.e., all the identified subgroups have large CrI centred at zero).

In Annex 2, the above analysis on GATEs is repeated by applying to each outcome variable the partitioning rules elicited for the other. This allows an investigation of the heterogeneous impact on GHG emissions across groups identified according to the partitioning tree of $\check{\tau}_i^{NI}$, and vice versa.

[Table 3 and Table 4 here]

[Figure 2 here]

Conclusion

The literature on the effectiveness of environmental policies that are voluntarily adopted sometimes overlooks their dual nature. They are intended to induce change in the behaviour of economic agents that eventually generate the desired societal outcome. However, what moves economic agents is the private advantage that can be achieved by adopting the policy. Considering this dual nature inevitably affects policy evaluation, that is, the assessment of policy effectiveness and efficiency. The present paper deals with this issue by focusing on the policy support for the adoption of organic farming and its impact on farm-level GHG emissions. The EU CAP measure for the 2015–2022 period and its adoption are investigated using a balanced panel of Italian farms.

The conceptual and methodological implications of these issues are also often neglected. These implications relate to the underlying logic of farmers' decision making and the consequent relevance of their heterogeneity, which implies a heterogeneous response to the policy intended as a treatment and, therefore, a heterogeneous treatment effect. A CML approach is adopted to estimate the IATEs and GATEs thus taking this heterogeneity, and its consequences for policy assessment, into account.

The results suggest that heterogeneity is critical and that, when properly considered, the estimates of the policy impact are weakly conclusive for the private outcome and almost inconclusive for the societal outcome. For some groups of farms these two outcomes of the policy support may even conflict, with a positive impact on private outcomes associated with a negative result for society. This has methodological and political implications and suggests potential directions for future research. On the methodological ground, the procedure for estimation of the IATEs and GATEs may be further refined, together with a deeper assessment of the robustness of results obtained and continuous improvements in the quality of data collection and variables definition. On the policy ground, if some conclusion had to be drawn, it would question the effectiveness of organic farming support as a tool to abate GHG emissions in agriculture. At the same time, the associated social cost seems remarkable if compared to conventional carbon pricing levels, thus pointing to some room for minimising this expenditure and improving policy efficiency. Since the evidence obtained in this respect is weak, these policy conclusions have to be treated with great caution and further confirmed.

References

- Abitabile, C., Marras, F., Viganò, L. (a cura di) (2019). Bioreport 2017-2018. L'agricoltura biologica in Italia. Rete Rurale Nazionale, Roma.
- Arata, L., & Sckokai, P. (2016). The impact of agri-environmental schemes on farm performance in five EU member states: A DID-matching approach. *Land Economics*, 92(1), 167–186.
- Baldoni E., Coderoni S., & Esposti, R. (2023). The productivity-environment nexus in space. Granularity bias, aggregation issues and spatial dependence within Italian farm-level data, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 415, 137847, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137847>

- Baldoni, E., Coderoni, S., & Esposti, R. (2021). Immigrant workforce and agriculture productivity: evidence from Italian farm-level data, *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 48(4), 805–834.
- Baldoni, E., Coderoni, S., & Esposti, R. (2018). The complex farm-level relationship between environmental performance and productivity. The case of carbon footprint of Lombardy farms, *Environmental Science and Policy*, 89, 73–82, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.07.010>
- Baldoni, E., Coderoni, S., & Esposti, R. (2017). The productivity and environment nexus through farm-level data. The case of carbon footprint applied to Italian FADN farms. *Bio-based and Applied Economics*, 6(2), 119–137, <https://doi.org/10.13128/BAE-19112>
- Baldoni, E. & Esposti, R. (2024). Estimating the impact of policies under spatial interference. The case of CAP support to organic farming. Department Working Paper n. 475, Università Politecnica delle Marche, Dipartimento di Scienze Economiche e Sociali.
- Bartolini, F., Vergamini, D., Longhitano, D., Povellato, A. (2021). Do differential payments for agri-environment schemes affect the environment benefits? A case study in Northeastern Italy. *Land Use Policy* 107: 104862.
- Bertoni, D., Curzi, D., Aletti, G., & Olper A. (2020). Estimating the effects of agri-environmental measures using difference-in-difference coarsened exact matching. *Food Policy*, 90, 101790.
- Betancourt, M. (2021). Prior Modeling. Retrieved from https://github.com/betanalphabet/knitr_case_studies/tree/master/prior_modeling, commit 56606fa62e35f87bc88cec6892b4a4d3587f7029.
- Blanford, D. (2024). The Vikings have landed – Denmark’s decision to tax livestock emissions as a ‘game changer. *EuroChoices* (in press). <https://doi.org/10.1111/1746-692X.12440>
- Brand, J. E., Zhou, X., & Xie, Y. (2023). Recent developments in causal inference and machine learning. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 49(1), 81–110.
- Breiman, L. (1984). *Classification and regression trees*. Routledge.
- Brown, C. Kovács, E., Herzon, I., Villamayor-Tomas, S., Albizua, A., Galanaki, A., Grammatikopoulou, I., McCracken, D., Alkan Olsson, J., & Zinngrebe, Y. (2021). Simplistic understandings of farmer motivations could undermine the environmental potential of the common agricultural policy. *Land Use Policy*, 101, 105136.
- Callaway, B., & Sant’Anna, P. H. (2021). Difference-in-differences with multiple time periods. *Journal of econometrics*, 225(2), 200-230.
- Carvalho, C., Feller, A., Murrery, J., Woody, S., & Yeager, D. (2019). Assessing treatment effect variation in observational studies: results from a data challenge. *Observational Studies*, 5(2), 21–35.
- Chipman, H.A., George, E. I., & McCulloch, R. E. (1998). Bayesian CART model search. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 93(443), 935–948.
- Chipman, H. A., George, E. I., & McCulloch, R. E. (2010). Bart: Bayesian additive regression trees. *Annals of Applied Statistics*, 4(1), 266–298.
- Clark M. A., Domingo N. C. G., Colgan K., Thakrar S. K., Tilman, D., Lynch J., Azevedo, I. L. & Hill, J. (2020), Global food system emissions could preclude achieving the 1.5° and 2°C climate change targets. *Science*, 370, 705–708.
- Coderoni, S. (2019). Il ruolo dell'agricoltura biologica nella mitigazione dei cambiamenti climatici. In Abitabile, C., Marras, F., Viganò, L. (Eds), *Bioreport 2017–2018. L'agricoltura biologica in Italia*. (pp. 131–143). Rete Rurale Nazionale.

- Coderoni, S., Dell'Unto, D., Cortignani, R. (2024). Curbing methane emissions from Italian cattle farms. An agro-economic modelling simulation of alternative policy tools. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 351, 119880.
- Coderoni, S., & Esposti, R. (2018). CAP payments and agricultural GHG emissions in Italy. A farm-level assessment. *Science of the Total Environment*, 627, 427–437.
- Coderoni, S., Esposti, R., & Varacca, A. (2024). How differently do farms respond to agri-environmental policies? A probabilistic machine-learning approach. *Land Economics*, 100(2), 370–397. <https://doi.org/10.3368/le.100.2.060622-0043R1>.
- Coderoni S., & Vanino S. (2022), The farm-by-farm relationship among carbon productivity and economic performance of agriculture. *Science of the Total Environment*, 819, 153103, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153103>
- Dabkiene, V. (2017). A comparative analysis of on-farm greenhouse GAS Emissions from family farms in Lithuania. *Research for Rural Development*, 2, 225–232, <https://doi.org/10.22616/rrd.23.2017.072>
- Dabkienė, V., Baležentis, T., & Štreimikienė, D. (2020). Calculation of the carbon footprint for family farms using the farm accountancy data network: A case from Lithuania. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 262, 121509, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121509>
- Dorie, V., Hill, J., Shalit, U., Scott, M., & Cervone, D. (2019). Automated versus do-it-yourself methods for causal inference: Lessons learned from a data analysis competition. *Statistical Science*, 34(1), 43–68.
- Eichorn, T., Schaller, L., Hamunen, K., & Runge, T. (2024). Exploring agro-environmental factors influencing adoption of result-based and collective agri-environmental measures: A PESTLE approach based on stakeholder statements. *Bio-based and Applied Economics*, 13(1), 47–91.
- Esposti, R. (2017a). The empirics of decoupling: Alternative estimation approaches of the farm-level production response. *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 44 (3): 499–537.
- Esposti, R. (2017b). The heterogeneous farm-level impact of the 2005 CAP-first pillar reform: A multivalued treatment effect estimation. *Agricultural Economics* 48 (3): 373–386.
- Esposti, R. (2024). Non-monetary motivations of agri-environmental policy adoption. A causal forest approach. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 352, 119992. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.119992>.
- European Commission (2021). *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on an action plan for the development of organic production*. (COM(2021) 141 final/2). European Commission.
- European Commission: Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development – Unit A.3. (2024). Rough estimates of the climate change mitigation potential of the CAP Strategic Plans (EU-18) over the 2023–2027 period – Summary report for 19 CAP strategic plans. European Commission.
- European Commission: Directorate-General for Climate Action, Bogner, J., Lam, L., Forestier, O., Finesso, A. et al., (2024) Pricing agricultural emissions and rewarding climate action in the agri-food value chain, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2834/200>
- European Court of Auditors. (2024). *Organic farming in the EU. Gaps and inconsistencies hamper the success of the policy* (SR-2024-19). European Court of Auditors. <https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications/sr-2024-19>

- Gelman, A., Stern, H.S., Carlin, J.B., Dunson, D. B., Vehtari, A., & Rubin, D. B. (2013). *Bayesian data analysis*. Chapman and Hall.
- Guerrero, I., Bielza Diaz-Caneja, M., Angileri, V., Assouline, M., Bosco, S., Catarino, R., Chen, M., Koeble, R., Lindner, S., Makowski, D., Montero Castaño, A., Perez-Soba Aguilar, M., Schievano, A., Tamburini, G., Terres, J., & Rega, C. (2024). *Quantifying the impact of sustainable farming practices on environment and climate*. European Commission, Joint Research Centre. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/20814,JRC137826>.
- Hahn, P. R., Murray, J. S., & Carvalho, C. M. (2020). Bayesian regression tree models for causal inference: Regularisation, confounding, and heterogeneous effects (with discussion). *Bayesian Analysis*, 15(3), 965–1056.
- Hill, J., Linero, A., & Murray, J. (2020). Bayesian additive regression trees: a review and look forward. *Annual Review of Statistics and Its Application* 7, 251–278.
- Hill, J., & Su, Y. S. (2013). Assessing lack of common support in causal inference using Bayesian nonparametrics: Implications for evaluating the effect of breastfeeding on children’s cognitive outcomes. *The Annals of Applied Statistics*, 1386–1420.
- Huber, R., Tarruella, M., Schäfer, D., & Finger, R. (2023). Marginal climate change abatement costs in Swiss dairy production considering farm heterogeneity and interaction effects. *Agricultural Systems* 207, 103639.
- IPCC. (2022). Summary for policymakers. In *Climate change 2022: Mitigation of climate change. Contribution of working group III to the sixth assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157926.001>.
- IPCC. (2006). *IPCC guidelines for national greenhouse gas inventories*. Prepared by the National Greenhouse Gas Inventories Programme, Eggleston H.S., Buendia L., Miwa K., Ngara T. and Tanabe K. (eds). IGES, Japan.
- ISPRA. (2021). *Italian greenhouse gas inventory 1990–2019. National inventory report 2021*. ISPRA.
- Jansson, T., Nordin, I., Wilhelmsson, F., Witzke, P., Manevska-Tasevska, G., Weiss, F., & Gocht, A. (2021). Coupled agricultural subsidies in the EU undermine climate efforts. *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy*, 43(4), 1503–1519.
- Knaus, M. C. (2022). Double machine learning-based programme evaluation under unconfoundedness. *The Econometrics Journal*, 25(3), 602–627.
- Kremmydas, D., Ciaian, P., & Baldoni, E. (2023). Modeling conversion to organic agriculture with an EU-wide farm model. *Bio-Based and Applied Economics*, 12(4), 261–304. <https://doi.org/10.36253/bae-13925>
- Le Gloux, F., & Dupraz, P. (2024). Upscaling environmental incentives in the Common Agricultural Policy: an assessment of the potential of transfers from the first to second pillar. *Bio-Based and Applied Economics*, 13(1), 27–48. <https://doi.org/10.36253/bae-14414>.
- Lechner, M. (2018). Modified causal forests for estimating heterogeneous causal effects. *arXiv*, 1812.09487.
- Lee, K., Bargagli-Stoffi, F. J., & Dominici, F. (2020). Causal rule ensemble: Interpretable inference of heterogeneous treatment effects. *arXiv*, 2009.09036.
- Li, F., Ding, P., & Mealli, F. (2023). Bayesian causal inference: A critical review. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A*, 381(2247), 20220153.

- Martín-García, J., Gomez-Limon J. A., & Arriaza, M. (2024). Conversion to organic farming: Does it change the economic and environmental performance of fruit farms? *Ecological Economics*, 220, 108178, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2024.108178>
- McElreath, R. (2020). *Statistical rethinking: A Bayesian course with examples in R and Stan*. CRC Press.
- Muller A., Aubert C. (2014) The potential of organic agriculture to mitigate the influence of agriculture on global warming – A review. In Bellon, S. and Penvern, S. (Eds.), *Organic farming, prototype for sustainable agricultures*. (pp. 239–259) Springer.
- Nie, X., Wager, S. (2021). Quasi-oracle estimation of heterogeneous treatment effects. *Biometrika*, 108(2), 299–319.
- Quemada, M., Lassaletta, L., Jensen, L. S., Godinot, O., Brentrup, F., Buckley, C., Foray, S., Hvid, S. K., Oenema, J., Richards, K. G., & Oenema, O. (2020). Exploring nitrogen indicators of farm performance among farm types across several European case studies. *Agricultural Systems*, 177, 102689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2019.102689>
- Schievano, A., Perez-Soba Aguilar, M., Bosco, S., Montero, Castaño, A., Catarino, R., Chen, M., Tamburini, G., Landoni, B., Mantegazza, O., Guerrero, I., Bielza Diaz-Caneja, M., Assouline, M., Koeble, R., Dentener, F., Van Der Velde, M., Rega, C., & Furlan, A. (2023). iMAP-FP dataset: An evidence library of the effects of Farming Practices on the environment and the climate. European Commission. <https://doi.org/10.2905/4e3c371a-be72-4ea0-aa0b-45f8cdda2064>
- Scialabba, N. E. H., & Muller-Lindenlauf, M. (2010). Organic agriculture and climate change, *Renewable Agriculture and Food Systems*, 25(2), 158–169 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742170510000116>.
- Sitarz, J., Pahle, M., Osorio, S., Luderer, G., & Pietzcker, R. (2024). EU carbon prices signal high policy credibility and farsighted actors. *Nature Energy*, 9, pages 691–702, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-024-01505-x>
- Skinner, C., Gattinger, A., Muller, A., Mäder, P., Fliebach, A., Stolze, M., Ruser, R., & Niggli, U. (2014). Greenhouse gas fluxes from agricultural soils under organic and non-organic management – A global meta-analysis, *Science of the Total Environment*, 468–469, 553–563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.08.098>
- Smith, L.G., Kirk, G.J.D., Jones, P.J. (2019a). The greenhouse gas impacts of converting food production in England and Wales to organic methods. *Nature Communications*, 10, 4641. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-12622-7>.
- Smith, O. M., Cohen, A. L., Rieser, C. J., Davis, A. G., Taylor, J. M., Adesanya, A. W., Jones, M. S., Meier, A. R., Reganold, J. P., Orpet, R. J., Northfield, T. D., & Crowder, D. W. (2019b). Organic farming provides reliable environmental benefits but increases variability in crop yields: A global meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 3, 82. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2019.00082>
- Stepanyan, D., Heidecke, C., Osterburg, B. & Gocht, A. (2023). Impacts of national vs European carbon pricing on agriculture. *Environmental Research Letters*, 18(7), 74016.
- Stetter, C., Mennig, P., & Sauer, J. (2022). Using machine learning to identify heterogeneous impacts of agri-environment schemes in the EU: A case study. *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 49(4), 723–739.
- Stolze, M., Piorr, A., Häring, A., & Dabbert, S. (2000). *The environmental impacts of organic farming in Europe*. University of Hohenheim, Stuttgart-Hohenheim.

- Stolze, M., Piorr, A., Häring, A., Dabbert, S. (2000). The Environmental Impacts of Organic Farming in Europe. *Organic Farming in Europe: Economics and Policy*, Vol. 6. University of Hohenheim, Department of Farm Economics, Stuttgart-Hohenheim.
- Stolze, M., Sanders, J., Kasperczyk, N., Madsen, G., & Meredith, S., (2016). *CAP 2014–2020: Organic farming and the prospects for stimulating public goods*. IFOAM EU, Brussels.
- Storm, H., Baylis, K., Heckelei, T. (2020). Machine learning in agricultural and applied economics. *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 47 (3): 849–892.
- Tuomisto H.L., Hodge I.D., Riordan P., Macdonald D.W. (2012). Does organic farming reduce environmental impacts? A meta-analysis of European research, *Journal of Environmental Management* 112, 309e320, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.08.018>.
- Uehleke, R., Petrick, M., & Hüttel, S. (2022). Evaluations of agri-environmental schemes based on observational farm data: The importance of covariate selection. *Land Use Policy*, 114, 105950, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105950>
- Wiltshire, J., Keesje, A., & Gill, D. (2023). Guidance to Member States in improving the contribution of land-use, forestry and agriculture to enhance climate, energy and environment ambition. European Commission: Directorate-General for Climate Action Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2834/19417>.
- Yeager, D.S., Hanselman, P., Walton, G.M., Murray, J.S., Crosnoe, R., Muller, C., Dweck, C.S. (2019). A national experiment reveals where a growth mindset improves achievement. *Nature*, 573(7774), 364–369.

Table 1 – Composition of the cross-section sample under investigation.^a

	N of units
Original balanced sample	3,899
Excluded (staggered treatment) ^b	927
Entire sample	2,972
<i>of which:</i>	
Always-treated ^c	297
Never-treated	2,675
Estimation Sample	2,187
<i>of which:</i>	
Always-treated	212
Never-treated	1,976

^a The 2015-2022 balanced panel is firstly extracted; then, for any unit, variables are computed as averages over the period.

^b Among excluded units we also consider farms receiving support in 2015 but that, in the following years (i.e., under the 2014-2022 regime), do neither explicitly report organic production nor receive the analogous support.

^c Among always-treated units we also consider farms receiving support in 2015 and that, in the following years, receive the analogous support at least once over the whole 2015-2022 period. The implicit assumption is that the policy under consideration behaves as an absorbing treatment. Thus, when for treated units the support is not observed in some of the post-2015 years this has to be simply attributed to some problem in data collection or in the administration of the measure. under the 2014-2022 regime.

Table 2 – IATE estimates for model (4)-(5) for both outcome variables: NI variation ($D\pi_i$) and GHG emission variation (DE_i).*

Treatment	$0 \notin \text{CrI}$	MAP > 0	MAP < 0	ATE > 0	ATE < 0	CrI ATE	
	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	(%)	lower	upper
NI – all observartions	6	80	20	92	8	-0.03	0.19
NI – only with $0 \notin \text{CrI}$	-	100	0	97	3	0.10	0.50
GHG – all observartions	0	25	75	27	73	-0.20	0.11
GHG – only with $0 \notin \text{CrI}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

* $0 \notin \text{CrI}$ indicates the proportion of IATEs' CrI that do not include zero. MAP > (<) 0 denotes the proportion of IATE with MAP greater (lower) than zero. ATE > (<) 0 indicates the posterior probability that the ATE is greater (lower) than zero. CrI ATE is the 95% CrI for the ATE.

Table 3 – GATE estimates for outcome variable NI variation ($D\pi_i$) as obtained with shallow regression tree fitted to the MAP IATEs.

Leaf	Description	GATE	95% CrI		90% CrI		n
			lower	upper	lower	upper	
A - Using NI Tree							
8	Share Grapes < 0.32 , Phosphate < 56, Gross Production - Livestock < 0.5	0,02	-0,11	0,15	-0,09	0,14	1102
9	Share Grapes < 0.32 , Phosphate < 45, Gross Production - Livestock >= 0.5	0,13	-0,05	0,33	-0,02	0,29	255
10	Share Grapes < 0.32 , Phosphate >= 56, Gross Production - Livestock < 0.5	0,11	-0,03	0,27	-0,01	0,24	500
12	Share Grapes = 0.32 to 0.69, Phosphate < 31	0,19	0,01	0,39	0,03	0,36	79
11	Share Grapes < 0.32 , Phosphate >= 45, Gross Production - Livestock >= 0.5	0,15	-0,02	0,32	0,01	0,29	70
13	Share Grapes = 0.32 to 0.69, Phosphate >= 31	0,22	0,03	0,42	0,06	0,38	57
14	Share Grapes >= 0.69, Phosphate < 62	0,25	0,04	0,45	0,07	0,42	96
15	Share Grapes >= 0.69, Phosphate >= 62	0,35	0,10	0,60	0,15	0,56	28
B - Using GHG Tree							
8	Share Cereals >= 0.16, Phosphate < 17, Farm Type = Annual or Mixed	-0,01	-0,19	0,17	-0,16	0,14	333
10	Share Cereals >= 0.16, Phosphate >= 17, Farm Type = Annual	0,07	-0,07	0,22	-0,04	0,19	275
9	Share Cereals >= 0.16, Phosphate < 17, Farm Type = Livestock or Perennial	0,04	-0,15	0,22	-0,12	0,19	302
12	Share Cereals < 0.16, Altitude = 2 or 3, Potassium < 40	0,12	-0,03	0,27	-0,01	0,25	269
11	Share Cereals >= 0.16, Phosphate >= 17, Farm Type = Livestock or Mixed or Perennial	0,08	-0,02	0,19	-0,01	0,17	431
13	Share Cereals < 0.16, Altitude = 2 or 3, Potassium >= 40	0,17	0,01	0,33	0,03	0,31	199
14	Share Cereals < 0.16, Phosphate < 59, Altitude = 1	0,13	0,01	0,27	0,03	0,25	290
15	Share Cereals < 0.16, Phosphate >= 59, Altitude = 1	0,21	0,00	0,42	0,03	0,39	88

Table 4 – GATE estimates for outcome variable GHG variation (DE_i) as obtained with shallow regression tree fitted to the MAP IATEs.

Leaf	Description	GATE	95% CrI		90% CrI		n
			lower	upper	lower	upper	
A - Using GHG Tree							
8	Share Cereals ≥ 0.16 , Phosphate < 17 , Farm Type = Annual or Mixed	-0,14	-0,39	0,13	-0,36	0,08	333
9	Share Cereals ≥ 0.16 , Phosphate ≥ 17 , Farm Type = Annual	-0,08	-0,29	0,13	-0,26	0,10	275
10	Share Cereals ≥ 0.16 , Phosphate < 17 , Farm Type = Livestock or Perennial	-0,08	-0,35	0,19	-0,31	0,14	302
12	Share Cereals < 0.16 , Altitude = 2 or 3, Potassium < 40	-0,04	-0,26	0,19	-0,22	0,16	269
11	Share Cereals ≥ 0.16 , Phosphate ≥ 17 , Farm Type = Livestock or Mixed or Perennial	-0,06	-0,21	0,09	-0,19	0,07	431
13	Share Cereals < 0.16 , Altitude = 2 or 3, Potassium ≥ 40	0,01	-0,21	0,24	-0,18	0,20	199
14	Share Cereals < 0.16 , Phosphate < 59 , Altitude = 1	0,04	-0,14	0,23	-0,12	0,20	290
15	Share Cereals < 0.16 , Phosphate ≥ 59 , Altitude = 1	0,09	-0,22	0,43	-0,17	0,37	88
B - Using NI Tree							
8	Share Grapes < 0.32 , Phosphate < 56 , Gross Production - Livestock < 0.5	-0,09	-0,27	0,10	-0,24	0,06	1102
10	Share Grapes < 0.32 , Phosphate < 45 , Gross Production - Livestock ≥ 0.5	0,01	-0,25	0,29	-0,21	0,24	255
9	Share Grapes < 0.32 , Phosphate ≥ 56 , Gross Production - Livestock < 0.5	-0,02	-0,23	0,20	-0,20	0,16	500
12	Share Grapes = 0.32 to 0.69, Phosphate < 31	0,03	-0,26	0,32	-0,21	0,28	79
11	Share Grapes < 0.32 , Phosphate ≥ 45 , Gross Production - Livestock ≥ 0.5	-0,05	-0,27	0,18	-0,24	0,14	70
13	Share Grapes = 0.32 to 0.69, Phosphate ≥ 31	0,02	-0,22	0,28	-0,19	0,23	57
14	Share Grapes ≥ 0.69 , Phosphate < 62	-0,02	-0,30	0,26	-0,25	0,21	96
15	Share Grapes ≥ 0.69 , Phosphate ≥ 62	0,07	-0,29	0,42	-0,22	0,36	28

Figure 1 – IATE estimates for the two outcome variables: a) NI variation ($D\pi_i$); b) GHG variation (DE_i).*

* Left panel: point estimates of IATEs (median line) ordered from the smallest to the largest. The upper and lower dots represent the posterior 95% CrI endpoints associated with each individual MAP point estimate. Central panel: distribution of the MAP point estimate displayed in the left panel. Right panel: Monte Carlo approximation of the full posterior distribution of ATE defined as in Equation (6).

Figure 2 – Shallow regression tree fitted to the MAP IATEs for the two outcome variables: a) NI variation ($D\pi_i$); b) GHG variation (DE_i).

ANNEX 1 – Covariates

Table A1 - List of covariates considered in the study.

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Unit of Measure</i>	<i>Variable</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>Unit of Measure</i>
Cost structure, size and economic endowment			Production Specialization		
Variable Costs	Numeric	euro/SO	Farm Type	Categorical	-
Fixed Costs	Numeric	euro/SO	Gross Production - Crops	Numeric	%
Processing Costs	Numeric	euro/SO	Gross Production - Livestock	Numeric	%
Insurance expenditure	Numeric	euro/SO	Gross Production - Transformed products	Numeric	%
Taxes	Numeric	euro/SO	Gross Production - Quality products	Numeric	%
Outsourced Services	Numeric	euro/SO	Veterinary Expenditure	Numeric	euro/SO
Gross Production	Numeric	euro/SO	Dairy Livestock	Numeric	n/SO
Rents (-)	Numeric	euro/SO	Meat Livestock	Numeric	n/SO
Rents (+)	Numeric	euro/SO	Feedstuff	Numeric	euro/SO
Non-Organic CAP support	Numeric	euro/SO		Crop Mix	
National support	Numeric	euro/SO	Grapes	Numeric	%
Net Value Added	Numeric	euro/SO	Olives	Numeric	%
Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA)	Numeric	ha	Meadows	Numeric	%
UAA – Owned	Numeric	%	Fruit	Numeric	%
UAA – Rented	Numeric	%	Horticulture	Numeric	%
UAA - Irrigated	Numeric	%	Cereals	Numeric	%
Total Capital	Numeric	euro/SO	Flowers	Numeric	%
Circulating Capital	Numeric	euro/SO	Leguminous	Numeric	%
			Industrial	Numeric	%
Environmental and geographical factors			Others	Numeric	%
Latitude	Numeric	degrees		Input Intensity	
Longitude	Numeric	degrees	Pesticide Expenditure	Numeric	euro/SO
Disadvantaged Area	Categorical	-	Nitrogen	Numeric	100Kg/ha
Altimetry	Categorical	-	Potassium	Numeric	100Kg/ha
			Phosphate	Numeric	100Kg/ha
Socio-Demographic Characteristics			Worked hours	Numeric	hours/SO
Young Farmer	Categorical	-	Salaries	Numeric	euro/SO

ANNEX 2 – GATE analysis on Cross Partitioning Groups

The analysis on GATEs is here repeated by applying to each outcome variable the partitioning rules elicited for the other. This allows an investigation of the heterogeneous impact on GHG emissions across groups identified according to the partitioning tree of $\check{\tau}_i^{NI}$, and vice versa. In the case of $\check{\tau}_i^{NI}$, the GATEs estimated using the groups identified on $\check{\tau}_i^{GHG}$ (Table 3, part B) show that, in general terms, groups with positive point estimates (bold values) for GHG emission also yield positive GATEs for NI. Specifically, as for the point estimate, all subgroups show a positive NI variation with the only exception being the group showing the largest decline in GHG emission, namely, farms cultivating more than 16% of their UAA with cereals, distributing less than 1.7 tonnes of phosphate fertilisers per hectare and focusing on either annual crops or annual crops and livestock breeding. The largest NI impact is observed for groups with the lower emissions reduction. In fact, the three groups showing a non-zero and positive variation in NI (i.e., groups whose CrI includes only positive variations) are associated with a slight increase in GHG emissions, as for the point estimate. For instance, and remarkably, by becoming organic, farms with a low share of land cultivated with cereals and located in flat areas would benefit from higher income even without the associated policy support but would also increase their GHG emissions.

In the case of $\check{\tau}_i^{GHG}$, the GATEs estimated on the groups identified with the partitioning for $\check{\tau}_i^{NI}$ (Table 4, part B) do not show any meaningful GATE (i.e., with a CrI not including 0); that is, for the farm subgroups that better predict the heterogeneity of the IATEs for NI, the adoption of organic farming does not conclusively reduce GHG emissions. Moreover, across the groups with an increasingly positive impact on NI, positive and negative variations of emissions alternate without any general pattern emerging.

These cross-partition GATE estimates have an interesting policy implication. Since groups showing a positive and larger growth in GHG emissions are also associated with a positive and increasing NI response, the results reveal a trade-off of sorts between the private and societal outcomes of support to organic farming. As discussed in Section 3, this implies that policy expenditure is potentially inefficient for units with a positive NI impact. More importantly, this expenditure is ineffective as it goes to farms that did not produce the expected social benefit.

This interpretation of the group-level results can be extended by looking at the marginal GATEs. These can be informative since the comparison between pointwise (or interval) estimates computed at different levels of some moderating variable ignores the potential correlation between IATEs at different moderator values. Therefore, once the relevant subgroups are identified, as illustrated above, the full posterior distribution of each pairwise group difference can be computed as follows: $\phi_{g_1, g_2} = \phi(\tau_{i|i \in g_1} - \tau_{i|i \in g_2})$, where g_1 and g_2 indicate any two subsets of $\check{\tau}_i$. It seems instructive here to assess leaf differences, that is, the difference between the GATEs originating from the last split at the terminal knot and followed by the difference between the four GATEs at the extreme right and extreme left of the dendrogram (see Figure 2). The results are reported in Table A2, where the CrI refer to the posterior distribution of the difference between pairs of GATEs.

In the case of NI, a comparison of the extreme leaves of the portioning tree confirms that the response is amplified; a differential treatment effect is expected to be larger where the heterogeneity of individual GATEs is high. The groups at the extremes of the NI tree differ, as revealed by the corresponding fully negative 95% CrI, and this differential effect is larger than for the individual GATEs. Once again, this evidence supports the findings above regarding the private outcome and corroborates the idea that the farmers' response to organic support (in

terms of private outcomes) can differ substantially across farm groups but remain within a very limited, or null, before-support income loss.

The group comparison also confirms that the response to the adoption of organic farming is minor (and the evidence in this respect is non-conclusive) when the societal outcome, namely GHG emission abatement, is considered. It is confirmed that none of the farm groups differs from the others in terms of emission variation induced by the adoption of organic practices. Although there seem to be some response heterogeneity, as confirmed by comparisons for which the differential treatment effect reaches -0.23 (between Groups 8 and 15 and between Groups 9 and 15), these differences are largely noisy and, as a result, inconclusive regarding the policy's actual effectiveness.

Table A2– Selected differences between the GATE (as defined in part A of Tables 4 and 5, respectively) for the variation of outcome variables NI ($D\pi_i$) and GHG (DE_i).

Comparison	GATE diff	95% CrI	
		lower	upper
NI variation ($D\pi_i$)			
8-9	-0,11	-0,24	0,01
10-11	-0,08	-0,22	0,03
12-13	-0,07	-0,19	0,06
14-15	-0,11	-0,24	0,03
8-15	-0,33	-0,56	-0,06
9-15	-0,33	-0,42	0,00
8-14	-0,22	-0,45	-0,03
9-14	-0,11	-0,37	0,12

GHG variation (DE_i)			
8-9	-0,06	-0,25	0,15
10-11	-0,05	-0,22	0,15
12-13	-0,07	-0,25	0,12
14-15	-0,06	-0,32	0,21
8-15	-0,23	-0,58	0,15
9-15	-0,23	-0,56	0,18
8-14	-0,17	-0,46	0,11
9-14	-0,12	-0,35	0,10

ANNEX 3 – Robustness Checks

In this section, we present a series of robustness checks to investigate the sensitivity of the results with respect to the overlap and unconfoundedness hypotheses discussed in Section 5.

3.1 Overlap

The first robustness check concerns the overlap assumption. We investigate common support using both the posterior distribution of the BCF algorithm and a purely PS-based algorithm. We begin by approaching common support through the posterior distribution of the fitted functions for the treated, $f(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i = 1)$, and the untreated, $f(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i = 0)$, as proposed in Hill and Su (2013) and Li et al. (2022). The basic idea behind this approach is that if, for some values of \mathbf{x}_i , there is little or no overlap, $f(\mathbf{x}_i, \cdot)$ will extrapolate in the treatment arm for which the information is missing. As a result, the posterior variance of the estimated $f(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i = t)$ will be larger than the posterior variance of $f(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i = t')$. We can, therefore, exploit the posterior standard deviation, $s_i^{p1} = \text{sd}(f(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i = 1))$ and $s_i^{p0} = \text{sd}(f(\mathbf{x}_i, t_i = 0))$ to check for poor overlapping regions using two simple tests. Suppose that, for some point in the covariate space, $\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{x}$, the observed treatment is $t_i = 1$. Then, we lack common support when (i) the squared ratio between s_i^{p1} and s_i^{p0} exceeds the 95% (or 90%) quantile of a chi-squared distribution with one degree of freedom or (ii) s_i^{p0} exceeds the maximum standard deviation among all s_i^{p1} . In the present analysis, no observations are discarded in either of the two cases.

The second robustness check for overlap follows the approach discussed by Nethery et al. (2019), which consists of a pseudo-nearest-neighbour method designed to match observations with comparable PS values. This algorithm has two parameters, a and b , with b regulating the number of PSs estimated from each treatment group that must lie within an

interval of length a (measured on the PS scale). Nethery et al. (2019) suggest default values of $a = 0.1$ and $b = 10$, but we impose more stringent criteria by setting $a = 0.05$ and $b = 15$. Table A3 shows the number of discarded units for both exclusion strategies. Our results are essentially insensitive to the excision criteria adopted to ensure common support.

Table A3 - IATE estimates of model (4)-(5) for both outcome variables after dropping non-overlapping observations (Nethery et al. (2019): NI variation ($D\pi_i$) and GHG emission variation (DE_i).*

	Full Sample				$0 \notin \text{CrI}$			
	MAP > 0	MAP < 0	CrI ATE		MAP > 0	MAP < 0	CrI ATE	
			Lower	upper			Lower	Upper
	(%)	(%)			(%)	(%)		
NI								
$a = 0.1, b = 10$	82	18	-0.02	0.20	100	0	0.10	0.47
$a = 0.05, b = 15$	82	18	-0.01	0.17	100	0	0.09	0.47
GHG								
$a = 0.1, b = 10$	25	75	-0.19	0.11	-	-	-	-
$a = 0.05, b = 15$	23	76	-0.17	0.08	-	-	-	-

* $0 \notin \text{CrI}$ indicates the proportion of IATEs' CrI that do not include zero. MAP > (<) 0 denotes the proportion of IATE with MAP greater (lower) than zero. ATE > (<) 0 indicates the posterior probability that the ATE is greater (lower) than zero. CrI ATE is the 95% CrI for the ATE.

3. 2 *Uncounfoundedness*

ML methods are designed to automatically create artificial stratifying variables that enrich the initial confounders set in a data-driven way. As discussed in Stetter et al. (2022) and Coderoni, Esposti and Varacca (2024), these synthetic constructs may, in turn, correlate with other unmeasurable farm features, making it easier to attain the unconfoundedness identifying assumption. Nonetheless, this assumption is still not directly testable. Therefore, we probe unconfoundedness through ad-hoc sensitivity analysis.

We accomplish this check by following the sensitivity analysis discussed in Stetter et al. (2022) and Coderoni, Esposti, and Varacca (2024) and re-estimate our BCF multiple times, each time manipulating the covariate set, \mathbf{X}_i . We begin with a recursive procedure in which we re-fit Models (4) to (5) after dropping, in sequence, the feature most predictive of the outcome

(in terms of relative frequency within the tree ensemble), the three most predictive features, and the five most predictive features; the detailed results are reported in Figures A1–A6. In general terms, the findings seem robust to different configurations of the covariate vector, \mathbf{X}_i indicating that the methods discussed in Section 5 are resilient to unobserved heterogeneity, provided that the latter is associated with the observed confounders. In other words, all the interactions and nonlinearities internally constructed by the forests seem to work as additional controls that correlate with the omitted variables, thereby compensating for their omission.

However, these tests above do not consider potentially omitted variables that are predictive of the outcome and treatment assignment but are not associated with any of the controls in \mathbf{X}_i . We thus run an additional test to investigate the role of endogenous unobserved heterogeneity. This procedure involves generating a random variable Z correlated with both the outcome variables (Y) and the treatment variable (T), and then including this in the vector of control variables, \mathbf{X}_i . If the distribution of the IATE proves stable when estimating Models (4) and (5) with this new set of confounders, the unconfoundedness assumption becomes more credible. As shown in Figure A7, our results do not change much where there is a weak or moderate correlation between Y , T , and the unobserved confounder, Z . However, where there is a stronger correlation, the distributions of the IATEs seem to diverge from those in Section 6.2. Specifically, the observed differences, particularly for the NI outcome variable, are larger when the correlation between the unobserved covariate and the treatment assignment is high. In such cases, our test shows that missing out on Z could generate over-conservative estimates where most of the estimated IATEs switch from being positive to zero. A similar pattern is evident in the results for GHG emissions, although the drift towards zero is less marked.

References

Coderoni, S., Esposti, R., & Varacca, A. (2024). How differently do farms respond to agri-environmental policies? A probabilistic machine-learning approach. *Land Economics*, 100(2), 370–397. <https://doi.org/10.3368/le.100.2.060622-0043R1>.

- Hill, J., Linero, A., & Murray, J. (2020). Bayesian additive regression trees: a review and look forward. *Annual Review of Statistics and Its Application* 7, 251–278.
- Hill, J., & Su, Y. S. (2013). Assessing lack of common support in causal inference using Bayesian nonparametrics: Implications for evaluating the effect of breastfeeding on children’s cognitive outcomes. *The Annals of Applied Statistics*, 1386–1420
- Nethery, R. C., Mealli, F., Dominici, F. (2019). Estimating population average causal effects in the presence of non-overlap: The effect of natural gas compressor station exposure on cancer mortality. *The Annals of Applied Statistics*, 13(2), 1242.
- Stetter, C., Mennig, P., & Sauer, J. (2022). Using machine learning to identify heterogeneous impacts of agri-environment schemes in the EU: A case study. *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 49(4), 723–739.

Figure A1. Estimated IATEs and corresponding 95% Credible Intervals using the full covariate set (left panel) and leaving out the most predictive feature (right panel). Outcome variable: NI.

Figure A2. Estimated IATEs and corresponding 95% Credible Intervals using the full covariate set (left panel) and leaving out the three most predictive features (right panel). Outcome variable: NI.

Figure A3. Estimated IATEs and corresponding 95% Credible Intervals using the full covariate set (left panel) and leaving out the five most predictive features (right panel). Outcome variable: NI.

Figure A4. Estimated IATEs and corresponding 95% Credible Intervals using the full covariate set (left panel) and leaving out the most predictive feature (right panel). Outcome variable: GHG.

Figure A5. Estimated IATEs and corresponding 95% Credible Intervals using the full covariate set (left panel) and leaving out the three most predictive features (right panel). Outcome variable: GHG.

Figure A6. Estimated IATEs and corresponding 95% Credible Intervals using the full covariate set (left panel) and leaving out the most five predictive feature (right panel). Outcome variable: GHG.

Figure A7. IATEs estimated by including up to 18 simulated unobserved confounders with an increasing degree of correlation with Y_i and T_i . Values along the y-axis indicate the correlation between Z_i and Y_i (first value before the comma) and the (biserial) correlation between Z_i and T_i : a) NI variation ($D\pi_i$); b) GHG emission variation (DE_i).*

* Each density plot represents the distribution of the IATEs' MAP, while (vertical) ordering and colouring reflect the distance between the “standard” covariate configuration (first value on the y-axis) and each of the 18 cases. This distance is calculated through the test statistics of a Kolmogorov-Smirnoff test: values close to zero indicate no difference between two distributions; values close to one indicate drastically different distributions.

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